

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ADT41 (JJ92), a short-duration Basmati rice for Tamil Nadu, India

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Basmati rices are reputed for their aroma and quality. Traditional Basmati rices are tall, low-yielding, photoperiod-sensitive, and susceptible to insect pests, diseases, and lodging. High-yielding Basmati varieties are cultivated in northwestern India.

ADT41, popularly known as JJ92, is a semidwarf Basmati developed at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai. It is a selection from a dwarf mutant of Basmati 370. It matures early (110 d), has acceptable Basmati rice quality, and is nonlodging and photoperiod-insensitive. It is moderately resistant to blast but susceptible to brown planthopper, leafhopper, bacterial blight, and bacterial leaf streak.

ADT41 yielded a mean of 4.2 t/ha in 44 trials at research stations and on farms (Table 1). The highest grain yield obtained was 10.6 t/ha in the Adaptive Research Trial, Kodumudi.

Most of the grain quality characteristics of ADT41 are comparable with those of Pusa Basmati 1, a high-yielding variety grown in northern India. ADT41 conforms to the minimum acceptable standards for Basmati quality (Table 2),

Table 1. ADT41 (JJ92) yields in Tamil Nadu, India.

Type of trial and year	Trials (no.)	Av grain yield (t/ha)
TNRRI, Aduthurai, 1990-92	4	3.9
Multilocation trial, 1991	4	3.0
Demonstration, at research stations, 1992	8	3.7
On-farm trial, 1992	8	4.6
Adaptive research trial, 1992	20	5.8
Total/mean	44	4.2

Table 2. Morphological and grain quality characters of ADT41 (JJ92).

Character	ADT41	Pusa Basmati 1	Basmati minimum acceptable standard
Plant height (cm)	95	90	-
Days to maturity (d)	110	130	-
1,000-grain wt (g)	24.2	18.8	-
Head rice recovery (%)	55.7	44.8	>40.0
Grain length (mm)	8.3	7.4	6.5
Grain length - breadth ratio	4.3	4.2	3.5
Grain length after cooking (mm)	11.4	12.0	10.0
Grain elongation ratio	1.4	1.7	>1.5
Volume expansion (g/g)	4.6	4.5	3.7
Gelatinization temperature ^a (alkali score)	6	2	5-6
Aroma	Mild	Mild	Fine, appealing smell

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

with grain length and L-B ratio much higher than the minimum standards. Cooked rice length averaged 11.4 mm. The mildly scented rice is soft and not sticky, making it well-suited for specialty rice products.

The Tamil Nadu State Variety Release Committee has released ADT41 (JJ92) for general cultivation during kharif (monsoon) season in Tamil Nadu. ■

Mahsuri derivatives developed: Kushal, Maniram, Bahadur, and Ranjit

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Kushal, Maniram, Bahadur, and Ranjit have been recommended for flood-free rainfed lowlands during winter season in

Assam. They were developed by crossing Pankaj and Mahsuri. The varieties are free of some of the undesirable traits of Mahsuri. They are fertilizer-responsive and moderately resistant to shattering. Kushal, Maniram, and Bahadur are resistant to blast. Important characteristics and yield data are presented in Tables 1 and 2. ■

Table 1. Main characteristics of varieties.

Character	Kushal	Maniram	Bahadur	Ranjit
Height (cm)	116	105	114	99
Duration (d)	150	150	155	155
Panicle length (cm)	25.8	26.5	27.7	27.5
1,000-grain wt (g)	23.1	21.6	20.2	17.4
Hulling (%)	78.0	79.5	79.0	79.5
Milling (%)	72.0	73.0	71.0	68.0
Head rice (%)	63.0	62.0	64.0	57.0
Amylose content (%)	22.67	20.12	22.71	22.99
Grain length (mm)	5.8	5.6	5.5	5.4
L-B ratio	3.4	3.3	3.6	3.5

Table 2. Yield data of the Mahsuri-derived varieties under multilocational testing. Assam, India, 1989-91.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)								
	Titabar ^a	North Lakhimpur ^a	Pambari ^b	Tinsukia ^b	Kalachand ^b	Mahakal ^b	North Lakhimpur ^b	Nowgaon ^b	
Kushal	5.8	4.3	5.8	3.6	6.1	4.5	2.5	5.5	6.3
Maniram	4.2	4.4	5.4	3.6	5.5	4.9	3.1	4.7	6.0
Bahadur	4.2	4.5	-	3.3	6.1	4.5	3.3	6.5	5.3
Ranjit	4.2	-	5.3	3.2	4.2	4.4	3.9	5.8	6.1
Mahsuri (check)	3.2	4.2	4.0	-	2.5	-	2.3	4.0	4.0

^aRARS. ^bField trial station. All tests were conducted in 1991 except those in Titabar, which were in 1989 and 1990.

On-farm evaluation of rice cultivars for spring season in the lower hills of Chitwan, Nepal

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Most farmers in the village of Kholaghari and a few in the village of Daletar in Chitwan, Nepal, have farmer-managed irrigation systems and can grow irrigated transplanted rice in the spring before the main season rice crop. Many farmers, however, keep their lands fallow or grow maize in the spring because suitable rice cultivars are not available and they are unsure whether an early rice could be grown successfully.

We evaluated six promising rice cultivars in irrigated bunded terraces of seven farmers' fields (six in Kholaghari and one in Daletar) from Mar to Jul 1992. Soil was sandy loam or loam, with 5.1-7.6 N, 0.03-0.06 kg available P/ha, and 10-58 kg available K/ha. Each farmer's field served as one replication; plots were 60 m². Two to three seedlings/hill were transplanted at the spacing used by the farmers. Fertilizers were applied at 60:8.8:16.6 kg NPK/ha. Half of the N and all of the P and K were applied as basal; the remaining N was topdressed at the grain-filling stage. The participant farmers completely managed the trials.

We found significant differences among rice cultivars for most characters. Chaite-2 and Ghaiya-2 yielded the most among cultivars (Table 1).

We requested the farmers to assemble to evaluate the trials after harvest. A matrix ranking was done on cultivar

Table 1. Mean grain yield and other agronomic characters^a of 6 early rice cultivars grown in 7 farmers' fields. Chitwan, Nepal, Mar-Jul 1992.

Cultivar	Productive tillers/m ² (no.)	Nonproductive tillers/m ² (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Days to heading (no.)	Days to maturity (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Chaite-2	75 ab	7 ab	115 a	66 a	97 a	4.8 ab
Chaite-4	73 ab	11 a	95 b	58 c	88 c	4.2 bc
Ghaiya-2	74 ab	8 ab	106 ab	62 b	93 b	5.2 a
Radha-2	58 b	6 b	95 b	53 d	84 d	4.2 bc
Radha-32	75 ab	7 ab	106 ab	63 b	97 a	4.1 bc
Farmers' variety ^b	84 a	8 ab	112 a	56 ab	98 a	3.9 c
CV (%)	21.2	48.2	13.1	3.6	2.9	15.7

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bDiffered among farmers. Two used Laxmi, while the others used CH45.

Table 2. Matrix ranking of early rice cultivars grown by participant farmers, Chitwan, Nepal, Mar-Jul 1992.

Attribute	Varieties					
	Chaite-2	Chaite-4	Ghaiya-2	Radha-2	Radha-32	Laxmi
Yield						
Grain	7	3	5	3	4	8
Straw	6	3	3	8	4	6
Tillering	7	4	5	3	4	7
Disease resistance	7	4	5	3	4	8
Insect resistance	7	3	5	3	4	8
Early maturity	4	6	5	7	4	4
Shattering	6	4	5	4	5	6
Threshing ease	4	6	5	7	4	4
Dormancy	7	3	5	4	4	7
Milling recovery	5	4	5	5	6	5
Grain weight	6	4	4	6	3	7
Cooking quality	6	5	5	4	4	6
Best variety:	Two farmers - Laxmi Rest of the farmers - Chaite-2					

attributes. Farmers were given 30 maize kernels and asked to allot them to show the relative differences among the cultivars for a particular attribute. After discussion, farmers agreed on how the maize kernels should be allotted. The same procedure was used for all attributes.

When asked which cultivar they would choose if they could only use one, two farmers chose Laxmi, while the rest chose Chaite-2 (Table 2). When asked which

cultivars they would plant next year, all of them chose Chaite-2 and Laxmi. The participant farmers reported that many other farmers visited their trials and asked for seeds of Laxmi and Chaite-2. We concluded that local farmers preferred these two cultivars.

Farmers considered Chaite-2 and Laxmi superior to the other cultivars, although we thought Chaite-2 and Ghaiya-2 were the outstanding cultivars. ■